

POLYCYSTIC OVARY SYNDROME AND THYROID DYSFUNCTION

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Abstract. Polycystic ovary syndrome (PCOS) is the most common endocrine and metabolic disorder in women of childbearing age and can cause metabolic disorders, infertility, increased anxiety and depression; as a result, it can severely affect the physical and mental health of fertile women. PCOS is a clinically highly heterogeneous disease with unclear etiology and pathogenesis, which increases the complexity of treatment. The thyroid gland has complex regulatory effects on metabolism, reproduction, and emotions and produces hormones that act on almost all cells in the human body. The clinical manifestations of PCOS are similar to some thyroid diseases. In addition, some thyroid diseases, such as subclinical hypothyroidism (SHPT), not only increase the incidence of PCOS, but also exacerbate associated metabolic and reproductive disorders. Interestingly, PCOS also increases the incidence of some thyroid disorders. However, the role of the thyroid gland in PCOS remains unclear. The aim of this review is to scrutinize the critical role of the thyroid gland in PCOS by summarizing the comorbidity of PCOS and thyroid disease and their joint role in metabolic disorders, related metabolic diseases, and reproductive disorders; and by analyzing the potential mechanism by which the thyroid gland influences the development and progression of PCOS and its symptoms.

Keywords: polycystic ovary syndrome (PCOS), subclinical hypothyroidism (SHT), metabolic disturbances, thyroid disease, childbearing age.

Introduction: Polycystic ovary syndrome (PCOS) is the most common endocrine and metabolic disorder in women of childbearing age, affecting 3-15% of women worldwide. (1, 2). PCOS causes reproductive disorders, metabolic disorders, and psychological problems, all of which can seriously affect the physical and mental health of these women (3). PCOS is a clinically heterogeneous disease; there are four specific phenotypes that vary according to age, genotype, race, and environmental factors. The four phenotypes of PCOS are categorized by three factors: polycystic ovarian morphology, anovulation, and hyperandrogenemia (4). The etiology and pathogenesis of PCOS remain unclear, primarily due to the heterogeneity of these phenotypes, which increases the complexity of treatment of this complex endocrine disease. The clinical manifestations of PCOS are similar to some thyroid diseases. A growing body of evidence shows that PCOS is associated with an increased incidence of thyroid disorders such as autoimmune thyroiditis (AIT) and subclinical hypothyroidism (SHT) (5, 7). Palomba et al. recently did a comprehensive review on PCOS and thyroid disorders (8). This review aims to explore the important role of the thyroid gland in PCOS by analyzing the co-occurrence of PCOS and thyroid disorders; summarizing the incidences of metabolic disorders, associated metabolic diseases, and

reproductive disorders; and exploring possible mechanisms of interaction between PCOS and thyroid diseases.

Hyperthyroidism

Graves' disease (GD) is the leading clinical cause of hyperthyroidism with a global incidence of 1.5 to 6.5 per 100,000 (11). The incidence tends to increase with age. It is predominantly considered an organ-specific autoimmune disease (11) characterized by infiltration of the thyroid gland by T- and B-lymphocytes that respond to thyroid antigens and the production of thyroid autoantibodies. The major thyroid autoantibodies are directed against thyroid hormone receptors, which can activate the TTH receptor, resulting in excessive thyroid hormone production. Therefore, patients with this disease usually have hyperthyroidism and diffuse thyroid enlargement (11).

The relationship between thyroid function and metabolic disturbances in PCOS. The severity of metabolic disturbances in patients with PCOS is related to the degree of thyroid dysfunction. If thyroid hormone levels are too high, hyperthyroidism will occur, with symptoms such as overeating, hunger, and exhaustion (5 , 7). Conversely, if thyroid hormone levels are too low, hypothyroidism will occur. Recent studies have shown that the incidence of hypothyroidism is higher in patients diagnosed with PCOS (11-14%) compared to controls (1-2%). Metabolic changes seen in both hypothyroidism and PCOS include insulin resistance, dyslipidemia, weight gain, and obesity (5 , 7). Compared with patients with PCOS with normal thyroid function, women with PCOS and subclinical hypothyroidism have higher triglyceride levels, fasting insulin levels, and HOMA-IR (8). Patients with a combination of PCOS and HT showed more severe metabolic abnormalities than patients with PCOS or HT alone. Women with HT and PCOS had higher BMI, fasting blood glucose, HOMA-IR, and cholesterol compared with the control or HT-only group. These results indicate that the combination of PCOS and hypothyroidism is associated with greater metabolic and hormonal changes. Metabolic changes seen in both hypothyroidism and PCOS include insulin resistance, dyslipidemia, weight gain, and obesity. Compared with patients with PCOS with normal thyroid function, women with PCOS and subclinical hypothyroidism have higher triglyceride levels, fasting insulin levels, and HOMA-IR. Patients with a combination of PCOS and HT showed more severe metabolic abnormalities than patients with PCOS or HT alone(8). Women with HT and PCOS had higher BMI, fasting blood glucose, HOMA-IR, and cholesterol compared with the control or HT-only group. These results indicate that the combination of PCOS and hypothyroidism is associated with greater metabolic and hormonal changes. Metabolic abnormalities in patients with PCOS and with subclinical or clinical hypothyroidism associated with AIT were significantly improved with thyroid function medication compared with patients with normal thyroid function(5 , 7).

Increased risk of DM2 complications with thyroid dysfunction in PCOS.

The link between PCOS and DM2 has been fully confirmed (6). For example, the study followed 148 patients with PCOS for three years; initially, none of the patients had diabetes and 18 (12%) had pre-diabetes symptoms. The study found that 5 (3%) patients developed DM2 and 47 (32%) women developed prediabetes symptoms (6). This association is important to monitor because the BMI of prediabetes patients tends to increase, and the deterioration of glucose tolerance in patients with PCOS may be exacerbated. An increasing number of studies have shown that hypothyroidism is associated with DM2. Brenta et al. found that the prevalence of hypothyroidism was higher in patients with DM2 than in patients without diabetes and that

complications of diabetes were more common in patients with DM2 than in patients without DM2, indicating that hypothyroidism may be associated with DM2 (6). For each increase in TTG, the incidence of DM2 increased 1.09-fold (14). A large study of Danish patients with thyroid disease (n = 19,199) showed that the prevalence of diabetes in Danish patients with PCOS was higher than in controls (12). Moreover, compared with the control group, the incidence of thyroid disease was higher in the group with PCOS, indicating that thyroid disease may influence the incidence of diabetes complications in patients with PCOS (12).

Reproductive health disorders.

Fertility disorders are one of the main characteristics of PCOS (2). Between 40-70% of female patients with PCOS are diagnosed with infertility, which is defined as failure to conceive after one year of regular unprotected sexual intercourse. Thyroid dysfunction also affects female fertility; therefore, fertility problems may be more frequent and severe in patients with both PCOS and thyroid disease than in patients with thyroid disease or PCOS alone(8,2).

Ovulation disorder, menstrual irregularity and reduced fertility.

Lack of ovulation is the most common type of female infertility caused by PCOS, and ovulatory disorders are diagnosed in 75-85% of PCOS patients; only about 30% have recurrent ovulation. Anovulatory infertility in women with PCOS is often associated with irregular menstruation. In adult women, both hypothyroidism and hyperthyroidism can cause menstrual irregularity and decreased fertility (7). Krassas et al. found that levels of sex hormone binding globulin (SHBG), estradiol (E2), testosterone, androstenedione, LH, and follicle-stimulating hormone (FSH) were higher in female patients with hyperthyroidism than in those with normal thyroid function. In addition, the menstrual cycle of women with hyperthyroidism was irregular with abnormal ovulation compared to healthy women in the control group. (7) Patients with hypothyroidism tended to have lower levels of SHBG, estradiol, testosterone and androstenedione and higher levels of prolactin than those with normal thyroid function. In the pre-puberty stage, hypothyroidism can lead to delayed puberty; it can also lead to irregular menstruation, breakthrough bleeding, low endometrial thickness, and ovulatory dysfunction. All receptors in the thyroid hormone function signaling pathway, including thyrotropin-releasing hormone receptor, thyrotropin receptor, and thyroid hormone receptors, have been found in the monkey uterus and have been shown to be affected by steroid hormones, suggesting that the thyroid gland plays a regulatory role in female fertility. Some studies have shown that hypothyroidism may be associated with the formation of ovarian cysts.

Insulin resistance in PCOS.

Insulin resistance and hyperinsulinemia play a key role in the development of PCOS, which in turn increases the risk of developing DM2, irregular menstruation and reproductive problems in PCOS patients. Regardless of BMI, the proportion of insulin resistance is significantly elevated in patients with PCOS compared to the general population. Insulin resistance associated with PCOS is characterized by reduced sensitivity and responsiveness to insulin-mediated glucose utilization, primarily in skeletal muscle and adipose tissue. Significant intrinsic factors are involved in the development of insulin resistance associated with PCOS, although in some cases it may be acquired due to exogenous obesity alone. The primary cause of PCOS is related to defects in intracellular insulin signaling downstream of the insulin receptor, which involves hyperphosphorylation of serine residues on the insulin receptor substrate protein 1, which then binds to the insulin receptor and initiates insulin-specific intracellular responses. Insulin resistance

is observed not only in peripheral tissues of patients with PCOS, such as adipocytes and skeletal muscle, but also in fibroblasts, granulosa cells, and ovarian theca cells. The study of patients with PCOS compared those with PCOS and corresponding BMI with subclinical hypothyroidism (SCH-PCOS group) to patients with PCOS and normal thyroid function, showing that the HOMA-IR of the SCH-PCOS group was significantly higher than that of the group with normal thyroid function. Additionally, the HOMA-IR in patients with PCOS and normal thyroid function was significantly higher than in the control group with normal thyroid function. Moreover, it was found that the HOMA-IR in patients with PCOS and hypothyroidism was the highest among all groups, and after receiving thyroid treatment, the HOMA-IR in PCOS patients with hypothyroidism decreased. These reports confirm the impact of hypothyroidism on carbohydrate metabolism parameters. Thyroid hormones are involved in regulating blood glucose levels at both central and peripheral levels. Centrally, T3 regulates glucose synthesis in the liver through the sympathetic nervous system. Peripherally, T3 enhances the expression of the glucose transporter GLUT-4 in skeletal muscle and downstream signaling cascade proteins responsible for glucose transport, thereby increasing insulin-dependent transmembrane glucose transport. Compensatory hyperinsulinemia observed in insulin resistance is closely associated with anovulation seen in PCOS. For example, insulin resistance in ovulating patients with PCOS is lower than in those with anovulatory PCOS. It has been shown that all treatments aimed at reducing insulin levels improve ovarian dysfunction and ovulation. Significant insulin resistance is believed to be associated with hyperandrogenism and acanthosis nigricans. The compensatory hyperinsulinemia of insulin resistance may allow the ovaries to partially avoid LH desensitization, leading to increased sensitivity of ovarian steroids to LH. Thus, these studies suggest the possibility that hyperinsulinemia may result in excess ovarian androgens.

Lipid Metabolism Disorders and Obesity in PCOS and Thyroid Dysfunction.

The thyroid gland regulates lipid metabolism. Reduced thyroid function often leads to lipid metabolism disorders, including obesity. Thyroid status is inversely proportional to blood lipid concentrations. T3 regulates the activity of several key enzymes involved in lipoprotein transport, such as cholesterol ester transfer protein and hepatic lipase, thereby influencing LDL distribution. Additionally, T3 can affect the synthesis and degradation of HDL. The promoter of the low-density lipoprotein receptor gene contains a T3 response element that regulates LDL receptor gene expression, thus increasing LDL clearance rates. This thyroid-controlled regulation may explain why patients with PCOS and hypothyroidism are prone to atherosclerotic cardiovascular diseases. Patients with PCOS are more likely to have subclinical hypothyroidism; since obesity is often observed in PCOS patients with subclinical hypothyroidism, obesity may be a causal factor in the relationship between PCOS and subclinical hypothyroidism. As obesity increases leptin levels, elevated leptin may stimulate the hypothalamus, leading to increased secretion of thyrotropin-releasing hormone (TRH).

Impact of BMI on Metabolic Parameters in PCOS.

The influence of PCOS on metabolic parameters is regulated by BMI. A minor thyroid hormone deficiency does not have a significant clinical impact on women with PCOS who have a low or normal BMI. However, in overweight or obese patients with PCOS, clinical symptoms develop in conjunction with preexisting conditions, even if the thyroid hormone deficiency is minor. Since PCOS symptoms can improve with weight loss, moderate weight loss (defined as a 5–10% reduction in initial body weight) may improve many PCOS characteristics, such as insulin

sensitivity index and hyperandrogenism. Recent evidence indicates that excess adipose tissue is a significant cause of excessive androgen and estrogen production. Sex hormone-binding globulin (SHBG), also known as testosterone-estradiol-binding globulin, regulates and controls the concentration of active androgen, specifically free testosterone, thereby contributing to symptoms of hyperandrogenism. SHBG primarily binds to testosterone but also binds to dihydrotestosterone (DHT), androstenediol, estradiol, and estrone. Zhu et al. found a significant correlation between TSH and insulin sensitivity, insulin secretion, and SHBG, but only in the high BMI group. In conclusion, PCOS is the most common endocrine syndrome associated with obesity in women. At least one-third of normal-weight PCOS patients exhibit abdominal obesity, while obese PCOS patients show a broader distribution of adipose tissue. Obesity promotes testosterone production through insulin resistance and circulating androstenedione while suppressing gonadotropin production, which plays a role in PCOS.

Conclusions

The clinical manifestations of PCOS resemble certain thyroid disorders. Thyroid conditions associated with PCOS primarily include subclinical hypothyroidism and Hashimoto's thyroiditis (AIT), while the coexistence of PCOS with hyperthyroidism is relatively rare. This association suggests that the thyroid gland may influence the clinical presentation of PCOS by affecting multiple systems, including metabolism and immunity. Insulin resistance is a widely recognized cause of PCOS, and thyroid function impacts the degree of insulin resistance. Specifically, hypothyroidism results in more severe insulin resistance compared to hyperthyroidism. Obesity significantly affects the health of modern populations, and patients with hypothyroidism are prone to obesity. Patients with PCOS accompanied by hypothyroidism tend to have high BMI and an increased prevalence of metabolic disorders. When thyroid function is restored in patients with PCOS or clinical hypothyroidism through thyroid treatment, their metabolic disturbances improve. Furthermore, the thyroid gland plays a vital role in reproductive disorders associated with PCOS. In summary, the role of the thyroid gland in PCOS is complex and involves multiple pathways. Thyroid function directly affects the clinical manifestations of PCOS, contributing to the heterogeneity of its clinical phenotype. Clinical reports have shown that some symptoms of PCOS have improved or even resolved with the restoration of thyroid function. These findings strongly suggest that the thyroid gland plays a critical role in the pathogenesis, development, and progression of PCOS. Therefore, patients with PCOS require careful screening, monitoring, and correction of thyroid function over time, which may improve or potentially prevent further worsening of PCOS symptoms.

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